

Rapid, portable, multiplexed detection of harmful algal toxins in freshwater

Sarah Bickman^{1*}, George Bullerjahn², Gregory Boyer³, Gregory Lewis¹, Cassandra Petrou¹, Brooks Macdonald¹, Seth Buchholz², Katelyn Barker², Jack Roser¹, Michael Lochhead¹

¹LightDeck Diagnostics, 5603 Arapahoe Ave, Boulder, CO 80303, U.S.A.; ²Bowling Green State University, 1001 E Wooster Street, 230 Life Sciences Building, Bowling Green, OH 43403, U.S.A.; ³SUNY College of Environmental Science and Forestry, 320 Jahn Laboratory Syracuse, NY 13210, U.S.A.

*corresponding author's email: sarah.bickman@lightdeckdx.com

Abstract

Harmful algal blooms are a significant threat to fresh waters necessitating routine testing to protect humans from exposure to contaminated drinking and recreational waters and for forecasting and modelling. Since toxin profiles change spatially and temporally there is significant need for rapid tests that can provide real-time, local answers. Currently, the four classes of toxins that are typically monitored in freshwater are microcystins (MC), cylindrospermopsins (CYN), saxitoxins (STX) and anatoxin-a (ATX-a). There is currently no method of measuring STX in freshwaters in the field and only a semi-quantitative test strip for ATX-a. A rapid, portable multiplexed test would reduce the time and cost associated with collecting critical data while improving human safety by ensuring that all four toxin classes are always monitored. The LightDeck technology enables portable, multiplexed detection of toxins and has been demonstrated in a duplex MC/CYN panel and is being expanded to include STX and ATX toxin classes.

Keywords: microcystin, cylindrospermopsin, saxitoxin, anatoxin-a, HAB, sensor, paralytic shellfish toxin

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Introduction

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) are a significant and growing problem threatening fresh waters globally. Cyanobacterial HABs contribute to more than \$2 billion in annual U.S. economic losses and the estimated annual cost of cyanobacterial HABs (CHABs) in western Lake Erie (WLE) alone exceeds \$65 million, which does not include the millions of dollars lost due to events like the Toledo water crisis. CHABs necessitate routine testing to protect humans from exposure to contaminated drinking and recreational waters and for forecasting and modelling. Since toxin profiles change spatially and temporally, there is significant need for rapid tests that can provide real-time, local answers (John *et al.*, 2019).

Currently, the four toxins that are most frequently monitored in freshwater are microcystins (MC), cylindrospermopsins (CYN), saxitoxin (STX), and anatoxin-a (ATX-a). STX causes paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) and ATX-a is also known as Very Fast Death Factor (VFDF). Currently available rapid tests for these toxins are semi-quantitative. STX has been documented in freshwater sources in the United States and worldwide (Wiese *et al.*, 2010; Savela *et al.*, 2015) and the frequency and distribution of STX-producing cyanobacterial blooms have been on the rise (Pearson *et al.*, 2016). In the United States, the 2007 National Lakes Assessment (NLA) revealed that 7% percent of U.S. lakes were impacted by STX (Loftin *et al.*, 2106). This is consistent with a recent California survey, which detected STX in 7% of wadable streams (Fetscher *et al.*, 2015) and in New York where STX toxins were detected in 15% of the blooms collected from inland

Fig 1. The LightDeck HAB Toxin MC + CYN System is shown along with a disposable multiplexed cartridge.

lakes (Smith *et al.*, 2019). A previous study from Lake Erie detected the *sxtA* gene, a gene involved in the synthesis of STX, in 12 of 18 samples from a *Dolichospermum* bloom in the central basin of Lake Erie in July of 2016 and 2017 (Chaffin *et al.*, 2019). In an ECOHAB-funded 2019 basin-wide survey of western Lake Erie (172 samples total), the *sxtA* gene has been detected in all of the 46 samples that have currently been analysed and it is expected that this number will increase as the remaining samples are analysed (Davis, 2019). In addition to widespread *sxtA* detections across the western and central basins of Lake Erie, saxitoxin was detected in surface scums in July 2017 at concentrations of 0.022 and 0.026 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Chaffin *et al.*, 2019). *Microseira* (basinonym *Lyngbya*) *wollei* mats are common in shallow zones of WLE (Bridgeman *et al.*, 2010) and this species has been shown to produce multiple variants of STX (Boyer, 2019; Smith *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, detection of ATX-a is also on the rise across the USA with reports from diverse locations such as California (Howard *et al.*, 2016; Bouma-Gregson *et al.*, 2018; Kelly *et al.*, 2019), New York (Boyer, 2007; Smith *et al.*, 2019), Washington (Hobbs

et al., 2019), Utah (Utah 2018), and WLE (Bouma-Gregson *et al.*, 2018; Smith *et al.*, 2019). Globally, ATX-a has been detected in countries such as Australia (John *et al.*, 2019), New Zealand (McAllister *et al.*, 2018), France (Gugger *et al.*, 2005), and Germany (Ballot *et al.*, 2010) to name a few.

While these toxins have been detected throughout the Great Lakes, currently the only way to collect quantitative data for STX and ATX-a is to have samples collected, processed in a lab and analysed by individual ELISA tests or shipped to laboratories that can perform LC-MS/MS analysis. The delay of laboratory analysis can unnecessarily expose people to toxins while testing is being conducted. Furthermore, performing multiple separate tests is time consuming, expensive, and occasionally necessitates decisions that limit the amount of testing. A rapid, portable, multiplexed test would reduce the time and cost associated with collecting critical data while improving human safety by ensuring that all four toxins are always monitored.

This tool will be an asset to water managers and community-based monitoring networks as they will have the ability to rapidly quantify the aforementioned cyanotoxins using this user-friendly platform. Furthermore, this tool will be incorporated into routine monitoring programs and experiments by academic, state and federal researchers to improve scientific understanding of HABs. Improved spatial and temporal understanding of HABs will allow for better models and improved predictive capabilities. In short, this technology is an improved scientific tool for management of freshwater sources, and is of particular relevance to the Great Lakes, where algal blooms are of significant concern.

This technology can be used to protect public safety by allowing for on-the-spot decisions about beach closures or whether a particular source of water should be used as the intake for a public water utility.

Here, we describe development of STX and ATX-a assays that will be integrated into a multiplexed assay with the existing LightDeck MC+CYN test (Fig. 1).

Material and Methods

The LightDeck platform uses planar waveguides illuminated by solid-state diode lasers that reproducibly couple light into the waveguide (Devlin *et al.*, 2013; Meneely *et al.*, 2013; McNamee *et al.*, 2014; Murphy *et al.*, 2015; Reverté *et al.*, 2017; Bickman *et al.*, 2018). Detection of all toxins uses competitive immunoassays where toxin-protein conjugates are printed on the waveguides using microarray technology and fluorophore-labelled antibodies bind to the printed spots as shown in figure 2.

Results and Discussion

The LightDeck MC and CYN assays were previously developed and were tested with natural water samples with expected correlations.

Preliminary development of an assay for saxitoxins (paralytic shellfish toxins) has demonstrated a sensitive assay with congener coverage that correlated well with the toxicity of the congeners. The 50% inhibition concentration is $1.2 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and the assay range is from 0.6 to $2.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ based on the 20% and 80% inhibition concentrations. In the quantitative range, the assay percent

Fig. 2. Top) A microarray image where spots in red are dye-protein fiducials, spots in blue detect MC, spots in green detect CYN, and blank spots are print buffer blanks. Bottom) Schematic of the competitive immunoassays to detect toxins. Toxin-protein conjugates are immobilized on the waveguide surface. The sample is mixed with detection reagents containing fluorophore-labeled antibodies, which will bind to the microarray spot when no toxin is present and bind to toxin in the sample when toxin is present.

coefficient of variation based on 6 replicates is 13%. Congener cross reactivity is calculated as the 50% inhibition concentration of STX divided by the 50% inhibition concentration of the congener (see Fig. 3). All results are preliminary and will be repeated when the assay is fully optimized.

Immunogen production for ATX-a is underway and will be used to create an antibody to be used in a competitive immunoassay.

In summary, a 4-plex assay for the simultaneous detection of the most common toxins in freshwater is underway. A rapid, quantitative, multiplexed test such as the one

described here will allow water managers to make faster, more informed decisions about water treatment.

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Congener	Toxicity (%)	LightDeck Cross Reactivity (%)
STX	100%	100%
C1&2	1%, 10%	18%
dcGTX2&3	15%, 38%	4%
dcNEO	Not known	25%
dcSTX	51%	16%
GTX1&4	99%, 73%	98%
GTX2&3	36%, 64%	66%
GTX5	6%	50%
GTX6	Not known	69%
LyngbiaWoller	Not known	25%
NEO	92%	189%

Fig. 3. Top) A standard curve measured for STX. Data is an average of three replicates \pm one standard deviation. Bottom) Preliminary congener cross-reactivity for saxitoxin.

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